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High temperature He bubble evolution and thermal stability of the WTaCrV refractory concentrated solid solution alloy

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we investigate the thermal stability and high-temperature evolution of He bubbles within the structure of the WTaCrV refractory concentrated solid solution alloy (RCSA), which is dedicated to nuclear fusion applications. The material was first irradiated with He⁺ ions to form nanometric He bubbles within its structure. Subsequently, their high-temperature evolution was studied using an in-situ heating method in a transmission electron microscope over a temperature range of 700 °C to 1000 °C. We found that the bubbles are stable in size up to a temperature of 700 °C and show no agglomeration up to 800 °C. At higher temperatures, the coarsening of the bubbles occurs through the migration and coalescence mechanism; however, even at 1000 °C, the size of the bubbles only slightly exceeds 1 nm. For a more in-depth understanding of the phenomena occurring during high-temperature annealing, molecular dynamics simulations were applied. We demonstrate that the low diffusivity of V_mHe_n clusters in the investigated WTaCrV alloy is responsible for the low tendency for high-temperature coarsening of the bubbles. The results of this study highlight the potential of the WTaCrV RCSA as a refractory, irradiation-resistant material for crucial components in future fusion reactors.

1. Introduction

Nuclear fusion is considered the future of sustainable energy production due to its undeniable advantages over fission technology, such as higher safety and efficiency, better fuel availability, and limited proliferation risk. However, developing this technology on a commercial level is one of the greatest challenges humanity is facing in the coming decades. Among many obstacles on this path, one of the most crucial concerns is finding new materials capable of operating under the unprecedented conditions present inside the fusion chamber [1]. From the perspective of materials science, one of the most exciting challenges is to develop materials for the construction of plasma-facing components (PFCs), including the divertor and first wall [2]. This is associated with its extremely harsh operating conditions, which include, among others, elevated temperatures (above 800 °C), intense irradiation damage (up to 200 dpa) and plasma exposure [12]. Irradiation damage in the materials

used in nuclear fusion technology originates from both the deuterium–tritium (D-T) plasma and the high-energy neutrons (14.1 MeV) produced in the fusion reaction [3]. The latter leads to the formation of numerous point defects that agglomerate over the lifetime of the material into extended ones such as dislocation loops or voids, leading to degradation of its mechanical properties [4]. Another factor significantly affecting the performance of materials operating in the nuclear fusion environment is helium irradiation. High fluxes of helium nuclei ($> 10^{23} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) are generated in fusion reactors as a result of the nuclear fusion reaction between deuterium and tritium [5]. This process leads to various degradation mechanisms of plasma-facing materials (PFMs), such as the formation of helium bubbles and voids, blistering, or a fuzz microstructure [6]. These factors can result not only in the degradation of the properties of the PFCs but also in plasma contamination, thereby causing instability in reactor operation [7].

Current investigations in the field of development of PFMs focus

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mainly on two aspects: improving the functional properties of tungsten, which is proposed as a PFM in experimental fusion reactors, or finding new materials with improved performance [789]. Despite many advantages of tungsten, such as high heat resistance, thermal stability, and low tritium uptake, it also has one critical disadvantage from the perspective of nuclear fusion – a low irradiation resistance [7]. The presence of extended defects in the form of dislocation loops has been previously reported for tungsten even at such a low damaging level as 0.01 dpa (displacements per atom) [10]. Their occurrence typically results in the degradation of the mechanical properties of the material or even irradiation-induced embrittlement [1]. Therefore, in recent years, various groups have been working on the development of new types of materials with improved irradiation resistance compared to tungsten. Among them, concentrated solid solution alloys (CSAs) seem to be the most promising candidates for new PFMs, because of their tunable properties, excellent mechanical properties, and extraordinarily high irradiation resistance [91112].

CSAs are alloys containing multiple alloying elements (typically three or more) at high concentrations (> 5 at.%), that form random solid solution systems, typically with a face-centered cubic (FCC) or body-centered cubic (BCC) structure [13]. These materials frequently exhibit unprecedented properties as a result of the high chemical disorder and lattice distortions arising from the presence of various elements in the crystal structure of the single solid solution. Among this relatively wide class of materials, BCC refractory CSAs (RCSAs) containing refractory alloying elements such as W, Ta, or Mo are nowadays considered to be the future of PFMs [8]. In recent years, various RCSAs systems have been studied from the perspective of their irradiation behavior, such as MoNbTaTiW [14], HfNbTaTiZr [15] or VCrWMoCo [16]. However, the applicability of a variety of such materials as PFMs is questionable considering the presence of high-activation elements such as Mo or Nb, which may significantly increase the decommissioning time of the PFCs [17]. Therefore, recently, a novel WTaCrV RCSA, containing only low-activation alloying elements, was developed [18]. The current studies in this field indicate the extremely high irradiation resistance of the WTaCrV-based alloys. For instance, El-Atwani et al. [18] showed that it is resistant to the formation of the extensive dislocations loops up to 8 dpa, during the in-situ TEM irradiation at the temperature of 800 °C. This is associated with the enhanced vacancy-interstitial recombination rate of the CSAs in comparison to the pure metals and conventional alloys, which was previously reported for the various CSAs [192021]. At the atomic level, variations in the local environment of the atoms in crystal sites affect the energies of the formation and migration of point defects, thereby decreasing their mobility and increasing recombination [13]. In our previous work [22], we showed that the WTaCrV RCSA exhibits high resistance against defect accumulation during He irradiation, considering both microstructural stability and irradiation hardening. However, critical knowledge about the behavior of He irradiation defects in this material at elevated temperatures, as expected for fusion reactors, is extremely limited. In the case of tungsten, the high mobility of He atoms in its structure at high temperatures leads to their agglomeration, resulting in degradation of material performance due to surface erosion, formation of large He bubbles, and/or helium-induced grain boundary embrittlement [2324]. Therefore, a thorough understanding of the mechanism of formation and evolution of He-induced defects in the newly developed WTaCrV RCSA, which is a critical issue for materials used in the fusion plasma environment, is essential for assessing its applicability as a PFM in the future fusion reactors.

Taking this into account, we performed room-temperature He⁺ ion irradiation of the equimolar WTaCrV RCSA to introduce a significant amount of He atoms into the crystal structure of this material. In the next stage, we used the in-situ TEM heating method for direct observations of the behavior of He bubbles at elevated temperatures. Our aim was to understand the kinetics of the evolution of He-induced defects as well as the phenomena that influenced their behavior. This was further

supported by molecular dynamics simulations, which provided a more in-depth analysis of defect kinetics in the studied material.

2. Experimental

2.1. Material fabrication and He⁺ ion irradiation

The investigated WTaCrV alloy was prepared with the application of the magnetron sputtering method, in the form of 1 μm layer deposited on a silicon wafer. The process was conducted at room temperature (RT) with a target power of 200 W (445 V) for 2 h and 35 min using the AJA International ATC 2400-V magnetron sputtering system. The substrate underwent rotation during the sputtering process to ensure uniform film thickness. For more detailed information regarding the fabrication process, please refer to [25].

In the next stage, the material was exposed to 200 keV He⁺ ions using the Danfysik Research Ion Implanter in the Ion Beam Materials Laboratory at Los Alamos National Laboratory. The energy of the He⁺ ions was selected in such a way as to obtain the highest concentration of He in the center of the layer (see Fig. 1). A fluence of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ was applied at a beam flux of $4.8 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. During the process, the specimen was fixed to a Cu block using carbon tape. The temperature of the sample was monitored by a thermocouple attached to the block, and no increase in temperature was detected during the process. The implantation occurred under vacuum, with the pressure maintained below 5×10^{-7} Torr.

Fig. 1 illustrates the damage profile and He distribution in the irradiated WTaCrV sample under the described conditions, calculated using the Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter (SRIM) software [26]. The simulations were performed in quick calculation (Q-C) mode using the standard “vacancy.txt” method, as it provides more reliable displacements per atom (dpa) values compared to the full cascade (F-C) mode, as described in more detail in [27]. To ensure good statistics, 10,000 incident ions were used. The angle of incidence for the ion beam was set to 0 degrees (ion beam perpendicular to the surface), and all ions were stopped within the target. In the simulations, the alloy composition was assumed to be equimolar, with all elements randomly distributed in the matrix. In complex alloys containing transition metals from various periods, exhibiting notable variations in atomic mass (e.g., periods 4 (Cr and V) and 6 (W and Ta)), SRIM predictions of dpa significantly rely on the input parameters [2829]. The calculations utilized the following displacement energies for the elements: W – 90 eV, Ta – 90 eV, Cr – 40 eV, and V – 57 eV [30]. A theoretical density of 12.3 g/cm³ and atomic density of $6.3 \times 10^{22} \text{ atoms/cm}^3$ (calculated by the SRIM) were applied. As shown in Fig. 1, the peak damage value of 0.6 dpa was located approximately 450 nm below the surface, while the highest He concentration occurs at a depth of 500 – 550 nm.

2.2. Material characterization

The investigated material was studied using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) with a JEOL JEM-F200 microscope operating at 200 keV, equipped with the dual SDD energy dispersive X-ray (EDS) system. In-situ heating studies were conducted using double tilt Gatan 652 heating holder. The temperature of the specimen holder tip was maintained using a tantalum bulk furnace in conjunction with a water-cooled specimen rod. The low thermal mass of the specimen furnace allowed for a rapid response to variations in heater current, ensuring efficient thermal regulation. A thermocouple, spot-welded to the furnace body, provided accurate temperature measurement. Temperature control was achieved using the Gatan Temperature Controller 1905, which maintained stable and precise thermal conditions during experiments. For each of the studied temperatures, a dedicated sample was used. A constant heating rate of 200 °C/min was applied for each temperature. The evolution of the He bubbles during heating was studied using the underfocus/overfocus technique with a constant defocus of 500 nm.

Fig. 1. Simulated displacement per atom (dpa) and He concentration as a function of depth for the He⁺-irradiated WTaCrV RCSA.

The thin samples for the TEM studies were prepared using the dual beam ThermoFisher Scientific Helios 5 UX scanning electron microscope (SEM) with the focused ion beam (FIB) lift-out technique. Standard cross-sectional samples were prepared for microstructural studies of the material. For the high-temperature studies, planar samples were used to avoid the effect of Si from the substrate. During the preparation, efforts were made to ensure that the observed area came from the depth with the highest He concentration (450 – 550 nm). The samples were mounted onto Mo grids to maintain high-temperature stability. To prevent Ga⁺-induced defects in the observed samples, the acceleration voltage of the ion column was gradually reduced during preparation, reaching finally 2 kV. Final polishing of the FIB-lamellas was conducted using the Gatan PIPS II Precision Ion Polishing System with Ar⁺ ions at energy of 2 keV and 500 eV, ensuring a sample thickness of 50–60 nm in the investigated areas (sample thickness was measured using the convergent electron beam diffraction (CBED) method).

2.3. MD simulations

We performed molecular dynamic (MD) simulations to gain a comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms behind He bubble growth in the WTaCrV RCSA. These simulations were conducted using the large-scale atomic/molecular massively parallel simulator, LAMMPS [31]. To describe the interatomic forces between metallic atoms, we employed the embedded atom method (EAM) potential developed by Zhou et al. [32,33]. The interactions between He atoms were modeled using the pair potential developed by Becker [34]. For the interactions between He and various metals, we utilized the pair potential formalisms suggested by Juslin and Nordlund (JN) [33,35,36]. To accurately describe short distances between atoms, all interactions were smoothly connected to short-range Ziegler-Biersack-Littmark (ZBL) repulsive interactions [26,33].

We initially constructed a single crystal of W, containing 2000 atoms with dimensions of 30.764 Å × 30.764 Å × 30.764 Å along the <100>, <010>, and <001> directions, respectively. Subsequently, we randomly replaced W atoms with Ta, Cr, or V atoms until we achieved the desired equimolar composition (W:Ta:Cr:V = 1:1:1:1). We applied periodic boundary conditions in all three directions. In all simulations, after creating the initial structure, each system was subjected to energy minimization using the conjugate gradient (CG) method to reach a minimum energy state. We then annealed the system at the target temperature and zero pressure conditions using the NPT ensemble for 8

ns.

Since vacancies play a significant role in the accumulation of He clusters, we considered different simulation settings. To capture the importance of vacancies in bubble accumulation, we created two series of simulation boxes. Each series included 10 boxes as described above. In each box, 2 % He (40 atoms) was randomly inserted into the WTaCrV simulation boxes. The difference between the first and second series is that in the second series, we randomly created 9 vacancies in each box. We then annealed them at 1000 °C.

To capture the growth of bubbles by annealing and to mimic the initial experimental setup, we manually inserted V₂He₈ clusters into the WTaCrV simulation boxes. In total, 2.5 at.% He atoms were inserted. Except for those He atoms that belong to V₂He₈, the others were randomly distributed. To ensure good statistical representation, we created 30 boxes where the local environment of the V₂He₈ cluster and the initial distribution of single He atoms varied. We annealed the boxes at 700 °C, 800 °C, 900 °C and 1000 °C, close to the experimental annealing temperatures. We followed the growth of the bubbles for up to 8 ns. We calculated the number of He (n) and vacancies (m) in the V_mHe_n clusters as a function of time in these systems. The growth of the vacancy fraction in the clusters was analyzed using Wigner-Seitz analysis. The visualization, cluster analysis, and Wigner-Seitz analysis were performed using OVITO software [37]. The binding energy of He atoms to the V_mHe_n clusters created by annealing simulations was calculated as follows (V_mHe_{n-1} + He → V_mHe_n) [33]:

$$E_b(V_mHe_n) = E_f(V_mHe_n) + E_f(He) - E_f(V_mHe_{n-1}) \quad (1)$$

$$E_f(V_mHe_n) = E_{def} - E_{per} + \sum_X C_X E_X^{ref} - nE_{He} \quad (2)$$

The formation energy of a He atom in the WTaCrV RCSA is denoted as $E_f(He)$, while $E_f(V_mHe_n)$ represents the formation energy of the V_mHe_n cluster. E_{def} and E_{per} are the total energies of the defective and perfect supercells, respectively. The parameter C_X refers to the number of atoms of species X removed to create a vacancy cluster with m vacancies, with E_X^{ref} being the reference energy of species X per atom in their pure BCC phase. The cohesive energy of close-packed helium is denoted as E_{He} [35].

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of the material and effects of He⁺ irradiation

Fig. 2a shows the bright field TEM (BF-TEM) image of the cross-section of the analyzed WTaCrV RCSA layer deposited onto Si substrate. It is clearly visible that the fabricated layer is homogenous, with no signs of extensive defects such as voids, and it adheres well to the substrate. In order to represent the distribution of the implanted He ions along the layer, the curve showing the concentration of He vs layer depth was superimposed on the image. The dashed lines on Fig. 2a indicate the He concentration peak area (450 – 550 nm), exhibiting the highest density of He bubbles. All considerations regarding the formation and HT evolution of He bubbles in this work will concern this area. To investigate the crystal structure of the analyzed material, selective area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns were obtained from three different areas of the layer (Fig. 2b–e): above, within, and below the He-peak, respectively. All the SAED patterns may be indexed as [001]_{BCC} zone axis, with no extra spots corresponding to the ordering or the secondary phases. Furthermore, the obtained patterns indicate no changes in the crystal structure of the WTaCrV alloy across the thickness of the layer, also in the He-peak area (Fig. 2c). This is also consistent with the EDS mapping, indicating the uniform distribution of all elements at both micro- (Fig. 2d) and nanoscale in the He-peak area (Fig. 2e). The measured concentrations of the alloying elements in the layer, determined by the EDS technique, correspond to the equimolar composition of WTaCrV: W (26 ± 1 at.%), Ta (24 ± 1 at.%), Cr (26 ± 1 at.%), and V (24 ± 2 at.%). The microstructural analysis in the He-peak area shows that the irradiation process resulted in the formation of the fine He bubbles within the structure of the studied material, as shown in Fig. 2g and Fig. 2h, using TEM under/over-focus method. The average bubble size reached 0.47 ± 0.13 nm. However, as described previously their formation did not result in the segregation of the alloying elements (Fig. 2e) or influenced the crystal structure of the material (Fig. 2c). More details concerning the microstructure of the material, the evolution of the He bubbles with the He⁺ ion fluence and their impact of the mechanical properties of the WTaCrV alloy may be found in our previous work [22].

3.2. He bubbles evolution upon the in-situ TEM heating

In order to study the evolution of the He bubbles at the elevated temperatures expected for the fusion reactors, the He-implanted WTaCrV RCSA was subjected to in-situ heating TEM studies. The investigations were conducted at four different temperatures of 700, 800, 900, and 1000 °C. For each of the temperature, an individual sample was used, and the observations were conducted for 1 h. The studies were focused both on the bubbles present within the matrix, as well as at the grain boundaries.

3.2.1. Behavior of the He bubbles within the matrix

Fig. 3 shows a series of underfocused TEM images acquired from the area of a single grain for the initial material and samples annealed at various temperatures for a constant time of 1 h. It is clearly visible that up to 900 °C the size of the bubbles increases only slightly with temperature. Larger changes are observed only at the highest temperature of 1000 °C; however, even in this case, the size of the bubbles remains in the nanometric range. On the other hand, annealing has not visibly affect the distribution of the bubbles — in each of the presented cases, the bubbles are uniformly distributed within the matrix. There is also no tendency for non-uniform growth of specific bubbles, as they appear to be of similar sizes.

For the qualitative representation of the evolution of the bubbles during the HT annealing, their average size in relation to the annealing time at each temperature has been calculated and presented in Fig. 4a. It shows that the bubbles are relatively stable up to a temperature of 700 °C, as there are no significant changes in their size during the annealing. In this case, the initial size of the bubbles is 0.48 ± 0.13 nm, and after 1 h at 700 °C, the bubbles achieved an average size of 0.55 ± 0.13 nm. However, beginning from the temperature of 800 °C, the slight changes in the average size of the bubbles with the annealing time are readily observable. At the temperature of 800 °C, the bubbles grow almost linearly in size from 0.48 ± 0.13 nm at RT to 0.74 ± 0.14 nm after the first 30 min, and then remain stable in size up to 1 h. Similar behavior is also observed for the temperature of 900 °C, for which the bubbles initially quickly grow from 0.48 ± 0.15 nm at RT to 0.86 ± 0.17 nm after 12 min. However, after this initial period, their growth is hindered, reaching an average size of about 0.9 nm after 1 h. In the case of the highest studied temperature of 1000 °C, the response of the

Fig. 2. BF-TEM image of the WTaCrV RCSA layer, with the superimposed He concentration curve calculated by the SRIM software and the He-peak concentration area marked by dashed lines (450 – 550 nm), with the corresponding SAED patterns (acquired from the areas of yellow circles b – d). STEM images of the layer with the corresponding elements distribution maps (EDS) from the area of the layer (e) and He-peak zone (f) – the exact location of the image is marked with a yellow square in Fig. 2e. Under-focus (g) and over-focus (h) TEM images from the He-peak area showing the presence of fine He bubbles. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. TEM images of the He bubbles in WTaCrV BCC-CSA after the He⁺ irradiation at RT and following in-situ TEM annealing at various temperatures for 1 h.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the average He bubble diameter (a) and density (b) as a function of heating time.

bubbles is still similar – the bubbles grow rapidly from 0.47 ± 0.13 nm to 0.99 ± 0.20 nm within the first 8 min. In the next stage, the bubble size stabilizes at about 1.0 nm after 20 min of heating. However, after this phase the bubbles again increase in size reaching 1.19 ± 0.23 nm after the 1 h. Fig. 4b shows the density variations of the He bubbles with annealing time at 800 °C, 900 °C, and 1000 °C. Unexpectedly, no changes in the density of the bubbles is observed for the temperature of 800 °C, despite the observed increase in their average size. However, at the higher temperatures – 900 and 1000 °C, the density of the bubbles decreases with the annealing time. It is important to note, that these changes are relatively small – not exceeding 13 % for the temperature of 900 °C and 25 % for 1000 °C. Considering the rapid expansion of the bubbles during the initial stage of annealing and the minimal changes in their density throughout this process, it is very likely that the evolution of the bubbles is influenced by the presence of very fine bubbles or He-vacancy clusters in the vicinity of the larger bubbles, which are not

detectable using the TEM method. During annealing, these small bubbles or He-vacancy clusters may coalesce with larger bubbles, resulting in an increase in their size without a significant increase in the overall bubble density, as indicated in Fig. 4.

A series of TEM images acquired during in-situ TEM annealing of the He⁺-irradiated WTaCrV RCSA at 800 °C are shown in Fig. 5. For the sake of clarity, only the selected images are presented, which were acquired after 2, 30 and 60 min of annealing. The movie covering the entire period of 1 h annealing can be found in the [supplementary materials – Video S1](#). The obtained results indicate that the fine structure of the He bubbles formed during the RT irradiation remains stable at this temperature. Although, as depicted in Fig. 4a, the size of the bubbles slightly increases with annealing time, there is no visible tendency for their agglomeration or preferential growth. In both cases (before and after the 800 °C/1h) the bubbles are uniformly distributed in the matrix, and there are no visible changes in their density, which is consistent with the

Fig. 5. The underfocused TEM images showing the evolution of the He bubbles in WTaCrV RCSA during the annealing at 800 °C. Refer to the supplementary materials (S1) for a video.

calculations presented in Fig. 4b. The remarkable stability of the distribution of the He bubbles at this temperature, becomes particularly clear when examining the enlarged images presented in Fig. 5. To facilitate discussion, several individual He bubbles were highlighted with the circles. When comparing the structure of the bubbles at the beginning of the experiment (2 min) and at its end (60 min), it becomes clear that the bubbles remain stable with annealing time. Even when examining a pair of closely located bubbles (marked with a green circle), there is no observable tendency towards their agglomeration.

The evolution of the He bubbles at the temperature of 1000 °C is shown in Fig. 6. Only the selected images acquired during the experiment are presented for the sake of simplicity. Nevertheless, the movie encompassing the entire period can be found in the [supplementary materials](#) – Video S2. In contrast to the previous case (800 °C), the changes in both the size and the density of the bubbles at the various annealing stages can be easily noticed. This is particularly evident when comparing the images acquired after 2 and 60 min at the 1000 °C. In this case, one can observe the coarsening of the bubbles along with the decrease of their density. Interestingly, at the first stage of the experiment – up to about 16–20 min – the structure of the bubbles seems to be similar. Although the size of the bubbles changes, their density appears to remain unchanged. The same conclusion can be drawn when considering the calculated changes in the size and density of the bubbles versus annealing time – refer to Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b. For instance, the average size of the bubbles has doubled after 16 min at 1000 °C (from 0.47 ± 0.13 nm at RT to 1.04 ± 0.16 nm after 16 min at 1000 °C), whereas their density decreased only slightly (Fig. 4b). However, after this period, the bubbles start to agglomerate, leading to the formation of significantly larger bubbles. Fig. 7 shows the magnified area of the WTaCrV RCSA during heating at 1000 °C. Following the evolution of the two groups of bubbles, marked with yellow and blue circles, one can

conclude that the bubbles are stable for around 16 min. After this time, the bubbles start to agglomerate. The group of a few bubbles in the blue circle forms one big bubble after 20 min of heating. On the other hand, a different group (in the yellow circle) remains separate after 20 min of heating but agglomerate by 30 min. After these events, the newly formed bigger bubbles remain stable (in position and size) for the remainder of the experiment (1 h).

In order to better understand the mechanism of the HT coarsening of the bubbles, Fig. 8 shows the subsequent frames acquired during in-situ heating at a temperature of 1000 °C. The images depict the process of the agglomeration of three bubbles (marked with the yellow circle). When bubbles are close enough to each other, they quickly form a single, large bubble. This indicates that the coarsening of the bubbles in the investigated WTaCrV RCSA at the studied temperature is controlled by the migration and coalescence (MC) mechanism.

3.2.2. Behavior of the He bubbles at the grain boundary

Fig. 9a and Video S3 ([supplementary materials](#)) show the evolution of He bubbles in the vicinity of the grain boundary during annealing at 800 °C. It is clearly visible that the bubbles decorate the grain boundary after RT irradiation, as their density is significantly higher in comparison to the matrix. However, their size are comparable – 0.47 ± 0.11 nm (grain boundary) and 0.45 ± 0.11 nm (matrix). As shown in Fig. 9a, the most significant changes can be observed at the very beginning of the annealing process. After only 2 min at 800 °C, the bubbles at the grain boundary become significantly larger compared to those observed at RT. Their growth is also significantly faster than that of those in the matrix – within the first 2 min of annealing, they reach a size of 0.73 ± 0.12 nm, whereas the bubbles in the matrix at this stage are 0.50 ± 0.14 nm in size. This means that the rapid growth of bubbles occurs either during the heating to the target temperature and/or immediately after reaching

Fig. 6. The underfocused TEM images showing the evolution of the He bubbles in WTaCrV RCSA during the annealing at 1000 °C. See the supplementary materials (S2) for the video.

Fig. 7. The underfocused TEM images showing the evolution of the He bubbles in WTaCrV RCSA during the annealing at 1000 °C.

it. Nevertheless, after the initial period of growth in relatively short time, the structure of the bubbles at the grain boundary remains stable, as shown by the images acquired after 30 and 60 min of annealing – Fig. 9a.

A similar effect is also observed at 1000 °C, as shown in Fig. 9b and the Video S4 (supplementary materials). A significant growth of the He

bubbles located at the grain boundary is observed in the initial stage of the annealing. In this case, the average size of the bubbles increases from 0.49 ± 0.10 nm at RT to 0.95 ± 0.15 nm after the first 2 min at 1000 °C. However, after this period, the size of the bubbles stabilizes at around 1 nm – Fig. 9b. In contrast to the previous case (800 °C) where the bubbles are stable in size and positions after the growth period, at 1000 °C the

Fig. 8. The process of agglomeration of the He bubbles in WTaCrV annealed at 1000 °C; images are showing the subsequent frames recorded during the in-situ heating.

Fig. 9. The underfocused TEM images showing the evolution of the He bubbles at the grain boundary in WTaCrV RCSA during the annealing at 800 °C (a) and 1000 °C (b). Refer to the supplementary materials (S3 and S4) for the videos.

mobility of the bubbles along the grain boundary can be observed. This includes both their movement along the grain boundary (see Video S4) and their coalescence, as shown in Fig. 9b for the two bubbles marked by a yellow circle. Nevertheless, in both cases, the presence of the grain boundary does not significantly affect the behavior of the matrix bubbles in its vicinity. Upon close examination of Fig. 9a and Fig. 9b, a very narrow bubble-free zone along the grain boundary develops during annealing. However, its thickness does not exceed a few nanometers. This region likely serves as a “feed” for bubble growth during the initial stage of the annealing. However, due to the overall low mobility of the bubbles, those located further away do not have sufficient energy to attach to the boundary and do not interact with it.

3.3. Thermal stability of the WTaCrV matrix

Fig. 10 displays the series of SAED patterns obtained from the investigated WTaCrV before and after in-situ heating experiments at three various temperatures. It is evident that the applied annealing conditions does not affect the phase composition of the material. In all studied cases, only the BCC phase is identified. Although only SEAD patterns with the $[100]_{\text{BCC}}$ zone axis are presented in Fig. 10, several

different orientations are also examined from this perspective. In all cases, no additional spots corresponding to the formation of secondary phases are found. This indicates the high thermal stability of the investigated WTaCrV alloy, at least up to 1000 °C. This finding is consistent with the analysis of the distribution of the alloying elements after the annealing. Fig. 10e illustrates the STEM-EDS elemental distribution maps acquired for the sample annealed at 1000 °C for 1 h. Notably, all alloying elements exhibit uniform distribution within the matrix, with no evidence of segregation. Similar conclusions can be drawn when analyzing the maps obtained for the samples annealed at other temperatures studied within this article (not presented here for clarity).

Fig. 11 illustrates the EDS elemental distribution maps and the EDS line scan analysis conducted in the area of the grain boundary for the samples subjected to in-situ annealing at 800 °C and 1000 °C. Although an elevated density of He bubbles in the area of the grain boundary may be found in the TEM images for the sample annealed at the temperature of 800 °C, no observable changes in the distribution of the alloying elements are observed. In contrast, at 1000 °C such changes can be easily observed in both, elemental maps and the EDS line scan analysis across the grain boundary – Fig. 11b. In this case, the HT annealing resulted in

Fig. 10. A series of the SAED patterns acquired from the initial WTaCrV RCSA (a) and after the in-situ TEM annealing at the temperature of 800 °C (b), 900 °C (c) and 1000 °C (d) for 1 h. STEM image of the matrix of WTaCrV RCSA after the 1 h at the temperature of 1000 °C (e) with the corresponding EDS elemental distribution maps.

the enrichment of the grain boundary in W and Ta, while the concentration of Cr and V in this region is depleted compared to the matrix. The recorded chemical instability of the grain boundary can be related to the Inverse Kirkendall Effect (IKE), resulting from the vacancy flux to defect sinks, such as grain boundaries [38]. This results in the depletion of the fast-diffusing components at the sinks and the enrichment of the slow-diffusing elements, as observed in this work. Although the investigated material exhibits high thermal stability, previous research identifies compositional striations in the form of short-range order (SRO). Similar to this work, areas enriched in W-Ta and V-Cr were observed, indicating a high affinity of W to Ta and Cr to V in this material [1839].

3.4. Molecular dynamics simulations of He bubbles behavior upon annealing

To gain a deeper understanding of the evolution of He bubbles during high-temperature annealing of the studied WTaCrV RCSA, molecular dynamics simulations were employed. In tungsten, the formation of He clusters without pre-existing vacancies is energetically favorable [33,35]. In the first part, we investigated the formation of He clusters with and without pre-existing vacancies (V) within the temperature range of 700–1000 °C in WTaCrV alloy. Fig. 12a and Fig. 12c show the initial distribution of He atoms at 1000 °C after 0.001 ns, with no vacancies and 9 pre-existing vacancies, respectively. Fig. 12b and Fig. 12d depict the distribution of He at 1000 °C after 7.8 ns. Our findings indicate that at 1000 °C, only a few He_2 clusters form without pre-existing vacancies. However, when single vacancies are present, He clusters can grow around these vacancies. This suggests that bubble growth is unlikely without pre-existing vacancies in this temperature range. Based on this result, and given that the initial size of bubbles before annealing is approximately 0.4 nm, we proceeded to anneal the simulation box with manually inserted V_2He_8 clusters.

Video S5 in supplementary materials shows the frames of the growing V_2He_8 bubble at 1000 °C up to 8 ns. Fig. 13 presents snapshots of the V_mHe_n clusters (where V is the vacancy, and m and n represent the number of vacancies and He atoms in the cluster, respectively) after 8 ns of annealing at 700, 800, 900, and 1000 °C. Fig. 13e and Fig. 13f display the mean number of He atoms and vacancies in the V_mHe_n clusters as a function of time for the four annealing temperatures. These values represent the averages from 30 different boxes, each with different local environments for the V_2He_8 clusters. Fig. 13 demonstrate that the increase in temperature results in larger V_mHe_n clusters. This phenomenon can be attributed to two factors. Firstly, the diffusivity of He atoms increases with temperature, raising the probability of He atoms joining the V_mHe_n clusters, thus increasing the number of He atoms (n) in these clusters. Secondly, as more He atoms join the small bubbles, they displace some atoms from their lattice sites, leading to an increase in the number of vacancies in the V_mHe_n clusters. This process repeats in a cycle. We did not observe the movement of V_mHe_n clusters within this temperature range, indicating that V_mHe_n clusters are immobile at these temperatures. To determine if adding a single He atom to specific V_mHe_n clusters is energetically favorable, we calculated their binding energy. We selected several V_mHe_n clusters from Fig. 13e and Fig. 13f during the bubble growth phase and tested 150 different cases to calculate the binding energy. Fig. 13g shows that the mean binding energy of these clusters ranges between 1–2 eV, indicating that the growth of these bubbles is energetically favorable.

To investigate bubble coalescence in this alloy, we created $V_{25}He_{53}$ (bubble 1) and $V_{16}He_{33}$ (bubble 2) bubbles with semi-spherical shapes. The distance between the surface atoms along the center of mass of these two bubbles was approximately 0.81 nm. Additionally, 8 He atoms and 4 individual vacancies were randomly inserted into the simulation box (Video S6 in supplementary materials). These two bubbles, along with their related environments (8 single He atoms and vacancies), were

Fig. 11. The STEM images of the grain boundary in WTaCrV RCSA after the 1 h at the temperature of 800 °C (a) and 1000 °C (b) with the corresponding EDS elemental maps and EDS line scan analysis.

Fig. 12. The distribution of He atoms in WTaCrV RCSA during annealing at 1000 °C: (a) and (b) when no vacancy is present, and (c) and (d) when 9 pre-existing vacancies were inserted. The green spheres represent He atoms, while the red, blue, yellow, and pink spheres represent Ta, W, Cr, and V vacancies, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 13. The snapshots of the bubbles and He atom distribution in WTaCrV simulation box after annealing at: (a) 700 °C, (b) 800 °C, (c) 900 °C, and (d) 1000 °C for 8 ns. The green spheres represent He atoms, while the red, blue, yellow, and pink spheres represent Ta, W, Cr, and V vacancies, respectively. The mean number of He atoms (e) and vacancies (f) in the V_mHe_n clusters as a function of time and the mean binding energy of several V_mHe_n clusters (g). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

formed separately in annealing simulations starting from V_2He_8 fine bubbles. To capture the interaction between these two bubbles within a limited MD simulation time (8 ns), we annealed this system at 1500 °C. After 6.5 ns, the single He atoms were absorbed by the bubbles. In this case, the size of the bubbles grew to $V_{44}He_{64}$ and $V_{23}He_{36}$, and the distance between them became slightly closer, about 0.76 nm (Fig. 14a). After 8 ns, bubble 2 coalesced with bubble 1, forming a larger bubble, $V_{65}He_{100}$ (Video S6).

To determine if this coalescence was due to the high diffusivity of the smaller bubble (bubble 2), we analyzed the trajectory paths for bubble 2 in two different cases: one when the second bubble existed (Fig. 14a) and another when bubble 1 did not exist in its vicinity (Fig. 14b). Fig. 14c and Fig. 14d indicate that this coalescence is not due to the high diffusivity of bubble 2, but rather due to the interaction between the two bubbles.

Further detailed analysis revealed a new mechanism for the coalescence of these two bubbles, which is represented in Fig. 15. The entire coalescence procedure can be seen in Video S6; however, to clearly show

the mechanism, He atoms from bubble 1 have been omitted in Fig. 15 for visualization purposes. This mechanism consists of two parts. In the first stage, some single He atoms from the smaller bubble join the bigger bubble (Fig. 15b), leading to the over pressurization of the larger bubble and resulting in a vacancy being located between the two bubbles (Fig. 15c). This vacancy acts as a junction, facilitating the movement of He atoms and related vacancies from the small bubble to the bigger bubble (Fig. 15d and Fig. 15e).

4. Discussion

Helium is generated in materials used in the nuclear industry primarily through transmutation reactions that emit α particles. It is almost insoluble in solids; therefore, it quickly agglomerates and forms extended defects in the form of He bubbles. Their occurrence typically results in the degradation of the performance of materials exposed to neutron irradiation due to, among others, hardening, swelling, and grain-boundary embrittlement [40]. From this point of view, plasma-

Fig. 14. (a) A snapshot of two bubbles in the WTaCrV simulation box. (b) A snapshot of a single bubble in the WTaCrV simulation box. The trajectory path of the center of mass of bubble 2 after annealing at 1500 °C: (c) in the presence of bubble 2 from snapshot (a) until 100 ps after coalescence with bubble 1, and (d) in the absence of bubble 1 from snapshot (b) up to 8 ns. The green small spheres represent He atoms, while the red, blue, yellow, and pink small spheres represent Ta, W, Cr, and V vacancies, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 15. Some snapshots showing the mechanism for the coalescence of two bubbles in the WTaCrV simulation box. To clearly show the mechanism, He atoms from bubble 1 have been omitted. (a) A snapshot before coalescence. (b) A snapshot showing 5 He atoms migrating from bubble 2 to bubble 1. (c) A snapshot showing a Cr vacancy playing the role of a junction between the two bubbles. (d) and (e) Snapshots showing the coalescence of the two bubbles. The green small spheres represent He atoms, while the red, blue, yellow, and pink small spheres represent Ta, W, Cr, and V vacancies, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

facing materials (PFMs) are even more susceptible to the negative effects of He. In fusion technology, He nuclei are not only formed in transmutation reactions within the material but also as a result of the fusion reaction of deuterium with tritium [3]. This requires an in-depth determination of the impact of He and He-induced defects on the performance of new materials dedicated to PFMs, as well as an understanding of the mechanisms of formation and evolution of irradiation-induced structural defects at the elevated temperatures expected in fusion reactors.

For this reason, we fabricated new equimolar, refractory WTaCrV alloy dedicated for fusion applications, which was then subjected to RT He ion irradiation. Typically, He irradiation at low temperatures (below $0.2 T_m$, where T_m is the melting temperature) results in the formation of fine He bubbles, as the mobility of He atoms and vacancies in this temperature regime is limited [41]. For instance, Miyamoto et al. [42] reported the occurrence of only small bubbles (1–2 nm) in W irradiated with He⁺ ions at temperatures below 500 °C. Similarly, fine He bubbles were found in various RT He-irradiated CSAs [9], such as CoCrFeNi (1–2 nm) [43], CrFeMnNi (1.5 nm) [44], and TiZrNbHfTa (1–2 nm) [45]. In the presented case, the bubbles after RT irradiation were slightly smaller, with an average size of about 0.5 nm. It is noteworthy that bubbles exceeding 1 nm in size were previously reported for W irradiated under similar conditions, serving as a reference point for the analyzed material [42]. This is most likely associated with the reduced diffusivity of the point defects in the structure of the studied WTaCrV alloy compared to W, as previously reported in [46].

For an in-depth understanding of the behavior of He bubbles in the investigated RCSA at elevated temperatures, the RT-irradiated material was subjected to in-situ TEM heating studies. The performed experiments indicate that the bubbles remain stable in size up to a temperature of 700 °C (Fig. 4a). This suggests that the diffusion of He atoms and point defects within this temperature range remains negligible. However, starting from a temperature of 800 °C, the size of the bubbles slightly increases with annealing time (Fig. 4a). Conversely, the calculated density of the bubbles with respect to annealing time (Fig. 4b) remains at a similar level throughout the experiment, indicating that the bubbles grow independently without agglomeration. These findings are further supported by TEM micrographs acquired at different stages of the annealing experiment (Fig. 5 and Video S1). No signs of diffusion or agglomeration of the bubbles were observed at this temperature. This implies that the bubbles likely grow by collecting He atoms, vacancies, and/or small bubbles (invisible in TEM) in their vicinity within the matrix. With increasing annealing temperature above 800 °C, a simultaneous increase in the average size of the bubbles and a decrease in their density can be observed. This phenomenon is especially visible at 1000 °C, where the average size of the bubbles increased from 0.45 nm to about 1.2 nm after 1 h of annealing. This was accompanied by a decrease in their density by about 25 %. The evolution of bubbles during annealing at 1000 °C is illustrated in Figs. 6 – 7 and Video S2. It is evident that the behavior of the bubbles at this temperature remains similar to the previous case to about 20 min – the average size of the bubbles increases; however, no agglomeration was observed. After this period, the bubbles started to agglomerate into larger ones, which is in good agreement with the increase on the bubble size vs. time curve. Previous research in this field identifies two primary mechanisms responsible for the HT coarsening of the He bubbles – Ostwald ripening (OR) and migration and coalescence (MC) [47]. The OR mechanism is prevalent at higher temperatures (above $0.5 T_m$) and results from the varying content of He atoms in the surroundings of small and large bubbles. This creates a flux of He atoms from the small bubbles to the large ones, causing their coarsening [48]. In contrast, the MC mechanism is active at lower temperatures (below $0.5 T_m$) and is based on the random migration of bubbles within the metal matrix. Coalescence can occur when two (or more) bubbles approach each other, resulting in the formation of a single larger bubble as shown in Fig. 8, the process of bubble agglomeration among nearby bubbles is very rapid, indicating

that this phenomenon is driven by the latter mechanism – migration and coalescence. However, in this case, no migration of the bubbles was observed before coalescence (see Video S2). This may indicate that the bubbles are approaching each other as a result of their size increasing by absorbing He atoms, vacancies, He-V clusters, or invisible He bubbles from the matrix, as described previously. Based on the obtained results, we propose the following mechanism for the evolution of He bubbles in the investigated WTaCrV RCSA at elevated temperatures (Fig. 16):

- In the first stage, the bubbles grow by collecting He atoms/vacancies from the matrix, as well as He-V clusters and/or small bubbles (invisible in TEM) from the vicinity.
- The continuous growth of the He bubbles causes them to approach each other until coalescence may occur.
- The bubbles reach their critical size, and they are sufficiently spaced apart to prevent agglomeration. To further increase their size, an elevation in temperature is required.

Unfortunately, accurately determining the melting temperature for the WTaCrV alloy in this study is challenging, and there are no literature data on this issue. However, an approximate value (based on the rule of mixtures) is 2570 °C. This corresponds to $0.45 T_m$ at a temperature of 1000 °C, which aligns well with the temperature range for the MC mechanism. MD simulations conducted on the nanosecond timescale did

Fig. 16. The mechanism of He bubble growth in WTaCrV RCSA. The description of each step can be found within the text.

not observe MC at $0.45 T_m$. However, when the temperature was increased to $1500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($0.59 T_m$), MC was observed after an initial growth phase of the bubbles. During this phase, a small number of He atoms appeared to migrate from smaller bubbles to a larger one, contributing to the initial growth of the larger bubble. This migration of He atoms, while not a typical OR process, led to the over pressurization of the larger bubble. This over pressurization, in turn, facilitated the migration and coalescence of the smaller bubbles into the larger bubble.

Notably, significantly larger bubbles were typically observed in various RT He-implanted structural materials after high-temperature annealing. For example, Chen et al. [49] reported the presence of bubbles with an average size of 7 nm in FeCrAl alloy after in-situ TEM annealing at $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h. Even larger bubbles, ranging in size from 15 to 30 nm, were reported for Hastelloy N after annealing at $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h [50]. Unfortunately, the literature concerning in-situ annealing studies of He bubble behavior in W and RSCAs is extremely limited. Therefore, materials subjected to high-temperature implantation were taken as the basis for further considerations. Shen et al. [51] reported the occurrence of bubbles with a size of 2.5 nm in tungsten irradiated with He^+ ions ($5 \times 10^{16}\text{ cm}^{-2}$) at $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Bubbles larger than 10 nm were observed in tungsten after He-irradiation ($5 \times 10^{16}\text{ cm}^{-2}$) at $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [42]. In the group of CSAs, bubbles with an average size of 4.3 nm were reported in the FCC-structured CoCrFeNi alloy He-implanted ($1.5 \times 10^{16}\text{ cm}^{-2}$) at $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [52]. Similarly, relative large bubbles were found in the BCC-structured TiVNbTa (6.6 nm) and TiVTa (11.9 nm) CSAs He-implanted ($1.5 \times 10^{16}\text{ cm}^{-2}$) at $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [53]. In the presented case, the He bubbles after RT irradiation and subsequent in-situ TEM annealing were significantly smaller — 0.8 nm ($800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1\text{h}$) and 1.2 nm ($1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1\text{h}$). Although HT irradiation cannot be directly compared with post-irradiation annealing, the obtained results indicate the promising resistance of the analyzed WTaCrV alloy to HT He bubble coarsening. This phenomenon could be linked to the high chemical complexity of the CSAs, which suppresses the formation of He bubbles, as previously reported for the FCC-CSAs [195455]. Recently, El-Atwani et al. [46] reported the high resistance of the non-equimolar nanocrystalline W35-Ta35-Cr15-V15 RCSA against He bubble formation during in-situ TEM irradiation at a temperature of $950\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ up to a fluence of $1.65 \times 10^{17}\text{ cm}^{-2}$. They found only small He bubbles, with size in the range of 2–3 nm. Noteworthy, significantly larger bubbles, with size of about 10 nm, were previously found in tungsten irradiated under similar conditions [56]. Similar conclusions were drawn by Cheng et al. [57] for in-situ TEM He-irradiated CrMoTaWV RCSA. However, in both of these cases, the materials were investigated in nanocrystalline form. In this scenario, the high density of grain boundaries, which act as sinks for irradiation defects, may alter their accumulation behavior. In this study, we conducted experiments on samples extracted from larger grains (micrometer range; more details can be found in [22]), thereby minimizing the influence of grain boundaries on the accumulation and subsequent HT evolution of He-induced defects within the WTaCrV matrix.

However, considering the importance of grain boundaries on the irradiation behavior of structural materials, annealing studies were also conducted in their vicinity (see Figs. 10 and 11; Videos S3 and S4). At both considered temperatures ($800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), the bubbles located at the grain boundaries quickly reached their critical size. Subsequently, their size remained unchanged and did not significantly exceed the size of the bubbles within the matrix. A similar effect was recently reported for in-situ TEM He-implanted non-equimolar WTaCrV [46], and was linked to the low diffusivity of vacancies in this system. The obtained results appear to confirm this observation, as no preferential growth of the GB He bubbles was observed. In this case, the rapid coarsening at the beginning of the experiment most likely resulted from the absorption of He atoms/vacancies or He-V clusters from the matrix near the grain boundaries. However, long-distance diffusion seems to be inhibited. In contrast, preferential coarsening of He bubbles at the grain boundaries was observed during in-situ TEM irradiation studies for tungsten [58]. This phenomenon was also reported for post-implantation annealed

FeCrMnNi CSA [44] and ODS-steel [59]. This observation is crucial for the applicability of the studied WTaCrV RCSA, as the agglomeration and coarsening of He bubbles at the grain boundaries typically result in grain boundary-induced embrittlement [60].

Considering the high-temperature behavior of the implanted He atoms within the structure of the WTaCrV studied, they appear to be mobile; however, they do not form larger clusters, as indicated by our MD simulations (see Fig. 12 and Video S5). In contrast, a high tendency for the clustering of He atoms, leading to the formation of bubbles, was previously reported for tungsten [61]. The previous study on He diffusivity in WTaCrV indicates that the diffusion barrier for He migration is significantly higher compared to tungsten — 0.156 eV for WTaCrV and 0.06–0.08 eV for W, respectively [4662]. This creates a rough energy landscape with numerous sites that can become bubble nuclei, thereby accelerating their nucleation and leading to the formation of small, uniformly distributed bubbles within the matrix [46]. However, our MD studies indicate that vacancies are primarily responsible for nucleating He bubbles, as the formation of He clusters is limited. This observation is crucial for understanding the irradiation resistance of the studied WTaCrV alloy. Previous studies have demonstrated its exceptional resistance against dislocation loop formation during heavy ion irradiation [18], attributed to an enhanced rate of point defect recombination resulting from their reduced mobility [63]. On the other hand, under the He irradiation, vacancies can quickly become nucleation sites for He bubbles, leading to the formation of a dense structure of fine He bubbles (as was shown for the RT implanted material – Fig. 2). Next, due to the severe lattice distortions observed in CSAs, the formed bubbles remain immobile, preventing their agglomeration via the MC mechanism at the elevated temperatures. This is clearly visible during our in-situ TEM experiments, which show no agglomeration of the bubbles up to a temperature of $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This is also in agreement with the MD simulations (see Figs. 12 and 14) — although the He atoms are relatively mobile in the matrix, they become immobile when they form He-V clusters.

5. Conclusions

The present studies investigate the thermal stability and high-temperature evolution of He bubbles in the WTaCrV refractory concentrated solid solution alloy. The obtained results indicate that the He bubbles remained stable in size up to a temperature of $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. However, agglomeration was not observed up to $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is associated with the low diffusivity of point defects in this temperature range, attributed to the high chemical complexity of the investigated material. With an increase in temperature to $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the agglomeration of bubbles via the migration and coalescence mechanism was observed. However, even at this temperature, the bubbles remained significantly smaller than those previously observed in tungsten and other concentrated solid solution alloys. Using molecular dynamics, we showed that He atoms are mobile within the structure of WTaCrV at the studied temperature range. However, in comparison to tungsten, they do not form agglomerates. In this case, vacancies are responsible for the nucleation and subsequent high-temperature evolution of bubbles. The low tendency for the coarsening of He bubbles in the structure of the WTaCrV alloy is associated with the low mobility of $V_m\text{He}_n$ clusters in its structure. Furthermore, the material studied is thermally stable up to $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, as no formation of secondary phases was found. These findings highlight the potential of the WTaCrV alloy as a refractory, irradiation-resistant material for the crucial components of future fusion reactors.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Damian Kalita: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Amin Esfandiarpour:** Writing – original draft,

Visualization, Validation, Software, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Iwona Józwiak**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Yanwen Zhang**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Jesper Byggmästar**: Writing – review & editing, Software. **Mikko J. Alava**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Łukasz Kurpaska**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **William J. Weber**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Philip D. Rack**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Jacek Jagielski**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2025.113751>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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